

DAVID KUNZLE (1936–2024)

by Ian Gordon

David Kunzle was an internationally renowned early modern art historian and emeritus professor at UCLA, where he taught from 1976 to 2009. For many comics fans Kunzle may best be remembered for

his 1975 translation and introduction to *How to Read Donald Duck*, a volume originally produced in Chile by Ariel Dorfman and Armand Mattelart in 1971.

Kunzle had eclectic interests, though. His own scholarship on comics included many books, most notably *The Early Comic Strip: Narrative Strips and Picture Stories in the*

European Broadsheet from c.1450 to 1825 (1973); *History of the Comic Strip, Volume II: The Nineteenth Century* (1990); *Father of the Comic Strip: Rodolphe Töpffer* (2007); and *Rebirth of the English Comic Strip: A Kaleidoscope, 1847–1870* (2021), as well as collected editions of Töpffer, Gustave Doré, and Cham (Charles Amédée de Noé). He published on numerous other subjects, including political imagery and corsetry.

Kunzle was truly a Renaissance man to the extent that for many years he participated as a gymnast and tumbler in the Agoura, California Renaissance Pleasure Faire. Indeed, Kunzle was the British universities gymnast champion in 1961 and 1962.

David traced his interest in comics to a moment when at age eight, and left to his own devices, he discovered a volume of Hogarth's engravings in a large cupboard at his grandfather's house. He proceeded to immerse himself in the work for hours at a time. Although he didn't read comics as a child, his interest in the history of art took him to study for a Ph.D. in London after an undergraduate degree at Cambridge and some time studying in Zurich. While at the Courtauld Institute for the History of Art he received a well-timed push from the distinguished Professor Ernst Gombrich to look at the way picture stories developed from Hogarth to Töpffer.

Kunzle undertook his research in numerous libraries and museums, including the Bode Museum in East Berlin, The British Museum, and the Cabinet des Estampes in Paris. He managed to get special access directly to material in cabinets and shelves, rather than have to go through the normal channels of requesting material to be delivered from storage to a research desk. These occurrences speak to Kunzle's tenacity and charm. Later he put these qualities to good use gaining access to the Disney archives and meeting with Carl Barks in person. Kunzle's charm extended to his generosity to other scholars, encouraging their work and lending or giving them research materials.

David moved to North America after completing his doctorate. He taught first in Toronto before moving to the UC Santa Barbara in 1965. Fired from there in 1973, for political activity against the war in Vietnam, he then taught at the California Institute of the Arts and Immaculate Heart College until winning an unfair dismissal case. He chose to join UCLA rather than go back to Santa Barbara.

In the introduction to his 1973 book Kunzle offered a definition of the comic strip as having four distinctive features: a sequence of images, a preponderance of image over text, appearance in a mass medium, and a topical moral narrative (that is, they had something to say about social issues). Kunzle thought his book would be overlooked and wrote, "It is customary to defend the publication of volumes as large as this one with the claim that they fulfill a long-felt, much declared scholarly need; I do not make any such claim." The need for Kunzle's book may not have been felt 51 years ago, but like so much of his work, the depth of the research and the strength of the arguments showed these books were very necessary to the point that they helped open a field of scholarship that still engages with the issues he raised.

Vale David Kunzle, comics scholar.

Ian Gordon has written broadly on comics; his recent work includes essays on the Puck cartoons of Rose O'Neill and the 1960s Batman TV series.